

SOCIAL MATURITY OF SCHOOL GOING ADOLESCENTS IN RELATION TO THEIR GENERAL WELL-BEING

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ABSTRACT

In the present research the investigator has analysed the relationship between Social Maturity of school going adolescents and their General well-being in total and also across different dimensions of General well being-physical, emotional, social and school. In the present study, descriptive survey method was employed to investigate the social maturity of school going adolescents in relation to their general well-being. 120 students (60 male & 60 female) were selected from government senior secondary schools, situated in rural and urban areas of Ludhiana district. The Rao's social maturity scale (2006) and General well-being scale by Kalia and Deswal (2011) was used to collect data for the present study. Results indicated a significant positive correlation between Social Maturity and General well- being (Total Sample). Significant correlation was also reported for social maturity and the four dimensions of General well-being - physical, emotional, social and school.

Adolescence is a vital stage of physical and mental growth of the human body and indicates the transitional period from childhood to adulthood. It is characterized by rapid changes in the overall aspects of the individual personality such as physical, mental, emotional, social, and moral facets. It is a time that requires attention, protection and meeting of special needs of adolescents. Thus, adolescence represents a sensitive developmental period in which psychological characteristics such as positive well-being may play a pivotal role in physical health (Hoyt et al., 2012). Numerous factors affect the development during adolescent years which in turn determine the maturity of the adolescent. Maturity itself has many domains like emotional, physical, social, spiritual and the like. The developmental changes in this period have a life long bearing on the adolescent. The maturity attained especially the social maturity of the adolescent significantly affects his relationships and balanced development.

Social maturity is defined as the willingness of an individual to take responsibility for developing his/her community. Social maturity encompasses attainments in several domains, including independent functioning, effective interpersonal communication, interaction and responsibility i.e.; contributing to the well-being of the society (Greenberg et al.,1975). Social maturity is an essential aspect of human life especially in school life. Socially mature individuals have confidence to face reality for their integrity and are well developed in discriminating power to make appropriate decisions about their personal and social life. Kegan (1984) a psychologist centering in the developmental realm at Harvard University was inspired by Piaget's stage theory, and gave his own stage theory centered on how an individual reaches social maturity. Social Maturity detaches itself from the biological development and is specifically related with social context. The above discussion clarifies that social maturity is influenced by many individual and environmental factors. One such individual factor is the state of General Well-Being felt by an adolescent.

General Well-Being is one of the most important aspects of human beings and a state of general Well-Being can be accomplished in terms of a healthy body with a healthy mind. General well-being as a construct refers to the harmonious functioning of the physical as well as psychological aspects of the personality, giving satisfaction to the self and benefit to the

society (Siwach, 2000). General well-being is defined as encompassing people's cognitive and affective evaluations of their lives (Karatzias, et al., 2006). In general the main focus of well-being is on health because health is the main condition of an individual in all aspects. It is a level of functional and/or metabolic efficiency of an organism, often implicitly human. World Health Organization (1948) defined health as a state of complete physical, mental, and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity, In the Ottawa Charter for Health Promotion, (1986) WHO stated that health is not an objective of living but is a resource for everyday life. The concept of health is of positive nature and encompasses social and personal resources, also not leaving behind physical capacities. The spiritual dimension on health was added much later in the WHO definition (Dalal & Misra 2006). The World Health Organization has also enlisted the main determinants of health as social, physical and economic environment and also a person's personal characteristics and behaviors. In general, the environment in which an individual lives is of great importance on his/her life quality and health status. The other term, quality of life is used to evaluate the general well-being of individuals and societies and should not be confused with the concept of standard of living as it is primarily based on income. Instead, standard indicators of the quality of life include not only employment and wealth, but also the built environment, physical and mental health, education, recreation and leisure time, and social belonging.

Shrivastava and Saxena (2005) conducted a comparison between social maturities of high and low achievers of secondary school pupils in different kinds of schools, Govt. of India undertaking, private and government schools selected randomly and found that social maturity of high and low achievers in different types of schools show significant differences. Shah and Biswas (2018) conducted a study on social maturity among higher secondary school students from Bongaon city of West Bengal. Purposive sampling technique was used for selecting schools whereas random sampling technique used for selecting school students. In this study, the researcher found no significant difference in social maturity of students in relation to their gender and localities. Malik and Nasir (2019) conducted a study on social maturity of B.Ed. pupil teachers in relation to their psychological hardiness. A sample of 200 pupil-teachers (100 males + 100 females) from Government College of Education and University of Kashmir was taken randomly The results revealed that there is a positive correlation between social maturity and psychological hardiness of B.Ed. pupil teachers and also showed a significant difference between social maturity and psychological hardiness of male and female pupil- teachers. Alli & Thia (2023) analysed relations between students' well-being and academic achievement and found that psychological well-being was negatively related to academic achievement, indicating that students who experienced more school-related stress performed higher than students who experienced less stress.

A careful appraisal of the above literature helps to conclude that social maturity has been found to be related to many variables like sociability, behaviour, personality, adjustment, parenting styles, socio economic status, academic achievement, gender and decision making. Similarly general well-being has been found to be related to self-esteem, peer relationship, religious beliefs and stress. Hence through the present study the investigator aimed to explore the relationship between these two variables among adolescents in Ludhiana district of Punjab. and school well-being dimension of social maturity among school going adolescents.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- i. To find the relationship between social maturity and general well-being among school going adolescents.

- ii. To find the relationship between social maturity and physical well-being dimension of general well-being among school going adolescents.
- iii. To find the relationship between social maturity and emotional well-being dimension of general well-being among school going adolescents.
- iv. To find the relationship between social maturity and social well-being dimension of general well-being among school going adolescents.
- v. To find the relationship between social maturity and school well-being dimension of general well-being among school going adolescents.

METHOD

In the present study, descriptive survey method was employed to investigate the social maturity of school going adolescents in relation to their general well-being. 120 students (60 male & 60 female) were selected from government senior secondary schools, situated in rural and urban areas of Ludhiana district. The schools were randomly selected but availability of students, favourable attitude of principal and convenience of the investigator were also taken into consideration while selecting schools of study. The Rao's social maturity scale by Nalini Rao (2006) and General well-being scale by Kalia and Deswal (2011) was used to collect data for the present study. Mean, Median, Skewness, Kurtosis, SD, t-test and coefficient of correlation were used for analysis of the data.

RESULTS

Relationship between Social Maturity and General Well-Being

The table given below shows the mean scores of Social Maturity (Total Sample) and General Well-Being and also the correlation between the two variables.

Table-1

Showing correlation between social maturity (Total Sample) and General well- being (Total Sample) among school going adolescents.

Variable	N	Mean	S.D.	Correlation	Null Hypothesis Accepted/ Rejection
Social maturity	120	206.49	54.08	0.68**	Rejected
General well-being	120	185.04 2	33.66		

**Significant at 0.01 level

Table 1 shows that the value of correlation coefficient obtained between social maturity and general well- being among school going adolescents is 0.68, which is significant at 0.01 significance level. Thus, the conclusion obtained that there exists a significant and positive correlation between social maturity and general well- being of adolescents.

The reason behind this finding could be that general well-being as a construct refers to the harmonious functioning of the physical as well as psychological aspects of the personality, giving satisfaction to the self and benefit to the society (Siwach, 2000). It is the experience of health, happiness, and prosperity. It includes having good mental health, high life satisfaction, a sense of meaning or purpose, and the ability to manage stress. individuals with high levels of well-being are more productive at work and are more likely to contribute to

their communities. This helps the adolescent to make judgements, decisions and take proper action in face of problems and critical issues. It also enables an individual to participate in cooperative activities without conflict with others. Such a position definitely increases the levels of social maturity of the individual.

Relationship between Social Maturity and General well - being (dimension wise) among school going adolescents.

The table given below shows the mean scores of Social Maturity (Total Sample) and General well- being (dimension wise) among school going adolescents.

Table-2

Showing correlation between Social Maturity and (Total Sample) and General well-being (dimension wise) among school going adolescents.

Variable	N	Mean	S.D.	Correlation	Null Hypothesis Accepted/Rejected
Social maturity	120	206.49	54.08	0.59**	Rejected
Physical well- being	120	37.82	10.33		
Social maturity	120	206.49	54.08	0.75**	Rejected
Emotional well- being	120	40.95	12.07		
Social maturity	120	206.49	54.8	0.78**	Rejected
Social well- being	120	56.2	15.23		
Social well- being	120	206.49	54.8	0.62**	Rejected
School well- being	120	50.07	13.26		

**Significant at 0.01 level

Table no. 2 shows that the correlation coefficient obtained between social maturity and physical well-being dimension of general well- being among school going adolescents is 0.59, which is significant at 0.01 significance level. Thus, the conclusion was obtained that there is a significant and positive correlation between social maturity and the physical well-being dimension of general well- being among school going adolescents. The reason behind such a finding could be that one of the biggest social benefits, caring for the physical well-being of the adolescent can ensure better social skills. Especially if adolescents participate in team sports or exercise with a group, they will develop greater empathy and social skills.

They will also make new friends and gain new social outlets. This results in a high level of social maturity in the individual.

Further the table shows correlation coefficient obtained between social maturity and emotional well-being dimension of general well-being among school going adolescents is 0.75, which is significant at 0.01 significance level. This implies there is a significant and positive correlation between social maturity and emotional well-being dimension of general well-being among school going adolescents. Such a finding can be explained as emotional well-being is the ability to be strong and generate the emotions that lead to good feelings. By building emotional well-being skills, adolescents can better cope with stress, handle emotions in the face of challenges, and quickly recover from disappointments. As a result, they can enjoy their lives a bit more and pursue their goals a bit more effectively and hence become socially mature.

The correlation coefficient obtained between social maturity and social well-being dimension of general well-being among school going adolescents is 0.78, which is significant at 0.01 significance level. Thus, it can be concluded that there is significant and positive correlation between social maturity and the social well-being dimension of general well-being among school going adolescents. The reason behind such a finding could be that social well-being is the ability to communicate, develop meaningful relationships with others, and maintain a support network that can help overcome loneliness. This implies that adolescents with high social well-being are high on these skills and become able to make judgments, decisions and take proper action in face of problems and critical issues that leads to high social maturity.

Analysing the coefficient of correlation between social maturity and school well-being dimension of general well-being among school going adolescents is 0.62, which is significant at 0.01 significance level. Implying thereby that there is a significant and positive correlation between social maturity and the school well-being dimension of general well-being among school going adolescents. This may be because of the reason that school well-being is the ability to actively and meaningfully engage in academic and social activities and having positive and supportive relationships with teachers and peers. Thus adolescents scoring greater on school well-being are high on these abilities and in turn having independent functioning, effective interpersonal communication, interaction and responsibility and thus become socially mature.

EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS

The above study has reported a significant positive correlation between Social Maturity and General Well-Being as a whole and dimension wise. The findings of the present study will definitely help educationists, policy makers, parents as well as other groups dealing with adolescents directly or indirectly to chalk out programmes formally or informally to enhance the General well-being in totality and in its different facets viz. physical, emotional, social and school well being of adolescents, to make them more socially mature, reduce their negative stress and shape their personalities so that whatever the society they live in should be a place worth living.

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